

Public Relations for the Faculty of Management Science in Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University

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Abstract—The objectives of this research were to investigate the knowledge and understanding of public relations principles for public relations officials of the office of the faculty of management science in Rajabhat Suan Sunandha University and to determine the approach of public relations for the Office of Faculty of Management Science. The questionnaire was utilized as a tool to collect data. Statistics utilized included frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and regression analysis. The results of the research showed that the public relations officials misunderstood on public relations principles. The lack of the perception in media of the target groups both in-house and outside caused the misunderstanding on the roles, mission, and responsibilities. It would be beneficial to public relations division and other divisions of the office of the faculty of management science to be trained and obtained more knowledge and skills on the public relations to support the public relations work for the organization.

Keyword—Faculty of Management Science, Public Relations, Rajabhat Suan Sunandha University

I. INTRODUCTION

PUBLIC relations is important, and it is commonly accepted that indicates the image of the company. The operation of all agencies, both public and private sector require publicity to disseminate information because publicity is causing creative cognition affect the correct understanding together it can create the participation between organizations and customer and will bring awareness to the stakeholder to trust faith cooperation and good relations. This implementation is one of the important tasks as well [1].

The company set the goal is to release important information to clarify the fact and give the knowledge & benefit to the target audience. As well as building relationships are good between agencies to individual target groups and the public in order to operate smoothly and achieve the mindset of customer and agency, institution or organization with the reputation and experience. Due to this reason, the success all of the public relations strategy as a tool to communicate with the target person and related parties by PR strategies include a clear implementation plan and practices in line with the vision, goals, and mission of the agency. [2]

In the year 2551, in the PR fields of Faculty of Management Science in Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University become very

famous, and a lot of the student apply for it. Due to this reason is required to publicize information up multiple formats. Therefore, this research is interested to learn and inform about the Public Relations for the Faculty of Management Science in Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University from students' perception to get information on the use of media relations for the students according to gender, age, educational level, age, and education around which such information is useful. And this information can be used to develop an improved public relations work and serve as a guide to determine the Faculty of Management Science strategic plan and arrange the budget to the public each year and aid the faculty to be effective for the target audience and to become a success in the next academic year. [3]

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Public Perceptions of Higher Education

In an analysis of 30 public opinion polls on higher education conducted between 1989 and 1992, Harvey and Immerwahr found that two-thirds of Americans believe that the primary reason for attending college is to obtain job training while only 17% said receiving a broad education is the principal reason for attending. In fact, the analysis found that the public views the major purpose of a college education to be job preparation and career advancement and 80% of the public believe that obtaining the American dream depends on completing college. In short, having a college degree is viewed as necessary to having the desired standard of living [4]. The authors observed that higher education in the United States has an abundance of good will. Americans believe university research makes important national contributions; 91% think that one of the important things colleges and universities do is help produce contributing members of society; 87% agree that colleges help make America more competitive.

Harvey and Immerwahr concluded that the public had a fairly sophisticated knowledge about the contribution higher education makes to the national economy and the economic benefits that accrue to individuals. Furthermore, the authors said that the public understood the contributions universities make through scientific research and how such research creates new technology [4]. The Kellogg Forum on Higher Education for the Public Good did not paint as rosy a picture of the public's perception of public higher education's contribution to the public good when it re-visited Harvey and Immerwahr's 1995 study.

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Rather than public benefits, the focus group participants and survey respondents consistently spoke about higher education in terms of its private, economic benefits to the individual. "By and large, the purpose of a college education was seen as securing better jobs and career opportunities." [5].

Although the general public recognizes the contributions that universities make to society (the public good), the Harvey and Immerwahr study and the Kellogg study suggest that the public values the individual and economic benefits that universities bestow upon their graduates. However, it knows less about the societal benefits universities produce and suggest that universities have to build a new covenant with the American people that is based on the land-grant model but is applicable to modern challenges confronting a more urban and diverse society. Indeed, the report produced by the Kellogg Forum on Higher Education for the Public Good [6] called for the higher education community to dialogue with the public to create a better understanding of the goals and aims of higher education. Public relations are perhaps the best framework to better understand the general public and other constituent perceptions of higher education since the core mission of public relations is to inform, educate and persuade individuals through the use of communication techniques designed to reach the public through the media.

Although public relations activities in the university date back to the early 1800s, it was not until 1897 when the University of Michigan formally established a publicity office that public relations became a recognized administrative department in an institution of higher education, a number of factors contributed to the expansion of public relations on college and University campuses including competition among institutions, the growth of the mass media, the increase in administrative units and changes in the role and responsibilities of university presidents." [7].

B. Consumer Decision-Making

The research of the bargaining purchase process is in terms of consumer choice. They define bargaining in the purchasing context as "a process by which two or more parties mutually define one or more attribute values for a product [8].

The authors also indicate that information uncertainty is what distinguishes a purchase in which attributes are bargainable from a purchase in which attribute values are fixed. Results of this study, conducted with MBA and undergraduate students, indicated that purchasers reduce the amount of information searched for in order to get a good deal when bargaining is an option. Also, if the range of values for each attribute was known, purchasers were less likely to use initial offers to discriminate between dealers and focused more attention on bargaining with sellers to reach a more favorable agreement between buyer and seller [9] and refute appeals and their effectiveness in consumer decision making. Ignore appeals are those who ask consumers to ignore a previous claim because it may not be true. Refute appeals specifically state that the challenged claim is false. Two experiments, one using parents of young children and the

other using undergraduates, were conducted in Israel. Three different types of judgments on the part of the consumers were studied. Global judgments were those which consumers made.

From the entire collection of product claims and discounting cues, challenged attribute judgments were those made when consumers were questioned directly about the attribute being challenged by the discounting cues. Non-challenged attribute judgments were those in which the consumer was asked about attributes not being challenged [10].

These authors also studied the way in which the message was encoded. Elaborative encoding involves a large number of associations between the challenged and non-challenged claims regarding the product; non-elaborative encoding involves few associations linking the two types of claims. Results from the two studies indicated that the influence on consumer decision making of the type of discounting appeal (ignore or refute) and the type of encoding differed, depending on the type of judgment. Global judgments produced an interaction between type of discounting cue and type of encoding. Challenged attribute judgments were strongly influenced by the type of discounting, but not by encoding, and non-challenged attributes were not influenced by the type of discounting used. The authors indicate that further research is necessary for this area to better understand the discounting phenomenon [11].

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Population and Sample

The population in this research are the student who applies for the Faculty of Management Science Rajabhat Sunandha University 2550-2551 to identify a group of 100 people working on the normal course and are classified by a working group of 100 people in a total population of 700 people. The sample used in this study, researchers selected a group using the Yamane at the confidence level of 96% of the total sample, 100 people were randomly and can be stratified as working groups of 50 people and not working for groups 50 students for four-year bachelor's degree. [12]

The instrument used in this study is the questionnaires. The questionnaire is a checklist of questions divide by 2 part parts: 1) a questionnaire about personal status, gender, age, occupation, income Father, mother, father, mother and revenue per year. 2) part consumer's perception about the faculty news release, type of media in the year 2550 with respect to the media, TV, newspapers, magazines, outdoor billboards Site Information. [10]

C. Data Analysis Methods

Statistics used in this research included frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation and simple regression analysis. Data were analyzed by using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences.

Fig. 1 Research Conceptual Framework

B. Data Collection

TABLE I
DEMOGRAPHIC OF RESPONDS

	Frequency	Percentage
Genders		
Male	62	62
Female	38	38
Total	100	100
Age		
17 – 20 year	70	70
21 – 30 year	30	30
Total	100	100
Occupation		
State enterprise employees	14	14
Government employee	22	22
Work as employee	28	28
Business Owner	8	8
Trading	24	24
No working	4	4
Total	100	100
Income		
90,000 – 100,000	30	30
110,000 – 150,000	46	46
160,000 – 190,000	19	19
200,000 Up	5	5
Total	100	100
Family Status		
Parents Together	51	51
Divorce	41	41
Father Deceased	4	4
Mother Deceased	3	3
Disable Person	1	1
Total	100	100

IV. FINDINGS

The first analysis of data on the status of the respondent's perception of Faculty of Management Science Rajabhat Suan Sunandha University in the year 2550 and the perception data through different types of students in a four-year study in 2551 is divided by 2 groups as a working group and not working group.

62% of the respondents were male, and 70% of them were aged between 17-20 years equaling, and 28% of their fathers' occupation were workers, followed by 33% trading. This is followed by the state enterprise employees in service parts and family income per year in the 110,000 baht - 150,000 baht, the second is at 9000 baht - 100,000 baht and the family status in

divorced families is up to 41% lower than those that are together.

TABLE II
REGRESSION OF PUBLIC RELATION

Public Relation	B	Std. Error	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	1.406	.212	6.623	.000		
Media Publications (x _{1.1})	.305	.043	7.089	.000**	.808	1.238
University Radio (x _{1.2})	.239	.048	5.003	.000**	.755	1.324
Website (x _{1.3})	.189	.049	4.002	.000**	.844	1.54
Word of Mount (x _{1.4})	.339	.059	6.003	.000**	.655	1.324
Telemarketing(x _{1.5})	.439	.043	7.003	.000**	.453	0.324
U-Channel (x _{1.6})	.139	.036	3.003	.000**	.255	3.324

Adjusted R² = .737

Regression of public relations on customer decision-making factors reveals the regression of public relations. The optimal equation generated using the stepwise regression analysis is found to be statistically significant at 0.000 level with an F value of 125.196. With the initial combination of four (4) independent variables (public relations factors), only one (1) came out to provide the greatest explanatory power to the optimal equation of the customer decision making. Adjusted R-Square: .737 F-Value: 125.196 Significance of F:.000 As indicated, word of the mount(x_{1.4}) predicts the customer decision-making positively. The beta coefficient (B=0.509) implies that for every standard unit deviation increase in word of the mount(x_{1.4}), there is a 0.509 standard deviation unit increase in customer decision making.

Media Publications affirmed the use and effectiveness of the advertising media as manifested in their almost equal mean responses to the following strategies: print, broadcast, on-line ads packaging, motion picture brochure booklets, websites and banners, billboards, posters display signs (X=3.71), point-of-purchase displays (X=3.63), audio-visual materials (X=3.64) and symbols and logos (X=3.70). Overall, the extent at which these media are utilized for promotion purposes is quite apparent and effective with a mean rating of 3.64

All the website (x_{1.3}) are effectively utilized as manifested from the equal mean ratings of the customer decision making. However, it is proven that this telemarketing (x_{1.5}) commonly gives the customers an option to pay through ATM machine. Overall, with a mean rating of X=3.61, the U-Channel (x_{1.6}) is apparently effective PR strategy for the Faculty of Management Science in Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University as well.

V. DISCUSSION

In summary, the students get information from the Word of Mout and university website has the highest average. The media publications found have an average less student will get information and contact the faculty from the phone. The most of the respondent are working group and found that the perception of both groups is same. Group work and group work Students exposed to information publicized on U-

Channel and initial inquiries from the faculty of management science with a phone call to ask the information has the highest average student decides to choose the faculty of management since because the information from the various exhibitions and lectures in the classroom is invaluable. This consistent with the study of Scholars like [10] suggest that universities have to build a new covenant with the American people that is based on the land-grant model but is applicable to modern challenges confronting a more urban and diverse society. Indeed, the report produced by the Kellogg Forum on Higher Education for the Public Good [11] called for the higher education community to dialogue with the public to create a better understanding of the goals and aims of higher education. Public relations are perhaps the best framework to better understand the general public and other constituent perceptions of higher education since the core mission of public relations is to inform, educate and persuade individuals through the use of communication techniques designed to reach the public through the media. [12]

VI. RECOMMENDATION AND FUTURE STUDIES

Future research should consider the difference of characteristics of the student's academic status in 2551 as a priority because that must be an impact to the validity of the result at all times. From this study, FMS PR should develop ways and means of publicity as well as the selection of a suitable approach to media perception of the target and build up relationships with all target audience and fulfill the public relations activities. But at the same time the current students must create a unique sense of community civilization to release it.

There should be research and development to create a database of information from the brilliant civilization that corresponds to the academic community.

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